

CONSTRUCTION OF A SOLAR POWER PLANT IN THE UNIVERSITY PARKING AREA: DIGITAL CONTROL AND APPLICATION IN STEM EDUCATION

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Abstract

This article examines the experience of integrating a 30 kW solar power plant, installed in the university campus parking area, into the educational process. As part of the project, educational and research activities were organized to develop students' research, engineering, and environmental competencies. The article describes the possibilities of using digital monitoring and remote control systems via the SolarMan SMART platform. It analyzes the importance and effectiveness of applying renewable energy sources within the framework of STEM education. This research has been/was/is funded by the Science Committee of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan (Grant No. AP23488947).

Keywords: green energy, solar power, STEM education, digital control, future specialists, educational process

Introduction

The growing demand for sustainable energy solutions has facilitated the integration of renewable energy sources, particularly solar power, into various sectors. In this regard, university campuses are becoming ideal platforms for the implementation of such initiatives [1]. Utilizing solar energy through photovoltaic systems offers dual benefits [2]:

- a reduction in the carbon footprint;
- practical learning opportunities for students in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) fields.

Constructing a solar power plant in a university parking area is a unique project that not only meets energy needs but also provides shade for vehicles and even enables the integration of vehicle-to-grid technology [3]. Installing solar panels on existing infrastructure such as building facades and rooftops ensures efficient energy generation in densely populated urban environments [4].

This approach not only helps create an eco-friendly campus but also enables efficient land use by combining energy generation with parking infrastructure. Furthermore, the implementation of digital control systems enhances the productivity and reliability of solar power plants by enabling real-time monitoring, automated regulation, and predictive maintenance processes. As a result, energy generation and its integration into the grid become significantly more efficient.

The digital control system is a key component of the proposed solar power plant, ensuring effective management, monitoring, and optimization of energy production and distribution. These systems ensure the reliability of plant operations and adaptability to changing conditions [5]. Choosing the right sensors and data collection systems is crucial for real-time monitoring and control of the solar power plant.

The construction of a solar power plant can serve as a practical platform for STEM education, offering students hands-on experience in renewable energy technologies, digital control systems, and sustainable engineering practices [6]. This project integrates subjects such as electrical engineering,

mechanics, computer science, and environmental science, providing students with practical applications of theoretical concepts. By actively participating in the design, construction, and commissioning of the solar power plant, students acquire skills in project management, teamwork, and problem-solving.

Despite the increasing number of studies on integrating renewable energy sources into the educational process, the use of actual solar power plants on university campuses as learning and research platforms remains underexplored. In particular, the potential for using digital control systems and monitoring platforms for educational purposes has not been fully realized. There is a lack of practical examples and methodological solutions demonstrating the effectiveness of organizing project-based and hands-on tasks in STEM education using real engineering equipment.

The main goal of this study is to describe and evaluate the experience of integrating a 30 kW solar power plant installed in a university parking area into the STEM education system through the application of digital control technologies and the SolarMan SMART platform.

Methodology

In this study, several interrelated methods were employed with the aim of effectively integrating the solar power plant into the university's educational process. First, the design phase began with an assessment of the structural characteristics of the university parking area and solar irradiance levels, while also considering local regulations and grid connection requirements. To ensure high system performance, bifacial solar panels and high-efficiency inverters were selected. As a key component of the project, a digital control system with real-time data collection, monitoring, and management capabilities was developed and implemented through the SolarMan SMART platform. This system optimizes energy production and enhances the reliability and stability of the overall setup. Additionally, in order to integrate the system into STEM-oriented education, practical workshops, research projects, and simulations were organized for students, aimed at developing their interdisciplinary and engineering skills. During the construction and installation phases, compliance with safety regulations and engineering standards was ensured. Upon commissioning, all components were thoroughly tested to verify their performance and compatibility.

Results

To support the university's green energy initiatives, a project was implemented to install a 30 kW solar power plant in the parking area. The implementation of the project consisted of several stages:

- Preliminary analysis and design;
- Structural and technical solutions;
- Installation of the digital control and monitoring system;
- Compliance with safety and standards;
- System testing and commissioning.

In the initial phase of the project, a detailed solar analysis was conducted, taking into account solar irradiation levels, shaded areas, the optimal tilt and orientation angles for panel placement, and prevailing wind directions. Based on this analysis, a solar radiation map was developed. Additionally, the feasibility of connecting to the local electrical grid, the regional climatic conditions, and relevant construction regulations were thoroughly examined. As a result of the design phase, supporting metal structures were installed in the most suitable area of the parking lot, onto which bifacial solar panels were mounted. These panels increase energy generation efficiency by capturing not only direct sunlight from above but also reflected light from below. To convert the generated DC electricity to AC, high-efficiency inverters were selected and equipped with appropriate protective devices (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The solar power plant established on the university campus

During the installation process, all engineering and construction activities were carried out in accordance with international and local safety standards. To ensure electrical safety, automated circuit breakers and grounding systems were installed.

The SolarMan SMART platform was integrated into the system to enable real-time data collection, monitoring, and remote control. Through this platform, the performance of the inverters, the efficiency of the solar panels, and the amount of generated and consumed energy can be monitored. Access to the system is available from anywhere via a mobile application, ensuring continuous control and convenience.

After the installation of all components was completed, the system underwent full testing [7]. The voltage and current characteristics of the panels were checked, and their compatibility with the inverters was verified (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Remote Control of Solar Power Plant Parameters and Its Application in the STEM Education Process

Research on solar power plants, integrated into the training of future specialists in engineering and technical fields, encompasses several key areas. Students carry out educational and research activities focused on energy efficiency, such as measuring the performance of solar panels, studying the impact of the angle of incidence, and analyzing the effects of heat and dust. In addition, students are provided with opportunities to optimize panel placement, use high-efficiency converters, integrate

energy storage systems, and apply solar energy systems in physics, engineering, and environmental science lessons. This enables the organization of project-based and laboratory work, economic and ecological analysis, and experience with digital control systems. Students also have access to the SolarMan SMART platform to monitor and control inverter performance. Through this system, young researchers can conduct online monitoring, analyze data, detect faults, and perform remote management. The SolarMan SMART server provides real-time information on inverter output, the amount of energy produced and consumed, and overall system efficiency (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The SolarMan SMART Server Oriented Toward STEM Education

Moreover, the mobile application allows users to monitor inverter indicators via smartphone or tablet, offering continuous access to system status. This is especially important for managing and analyzing the efficiency of solar power plants. Such experiences help bridge theoretical knowledge with real-world application, foster the development of research skills, and deepen students' understanding of the importance of renewable energy sources. This initiative significantly contributes to the development of green energy on the university campus and supports the achievement of sustainable development goals. The 30 kW solar power plant enhances the campus's energy independence by producing electricity and promotes the use of clean energy sources.

Conclusion

Active student involvement in the project contributed significantly to the development of their engineering, research, and interdisciplinary competencies. Working directly with real engineering equipment and engaging in design and management processes laid a strong foundation for their future professional growth. Furthermore, using digital control technologies for educational purposes strengthened the connection between theory and practice, becoming a key tool for enhancing the quality of education. Thus, the integration of a solar power plant into the university's infrastructure is not only an efficient use of renewable energy sources but also represents an innovative model for delivering high-quality, modern, and practice-oriented STEM education. This experience can serve as a model for other educational institutions in the future and be regarded as a concrete tool for achieving sustainable development goals.

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